

Ecology inside a host: hazard curvature and time-to-event theory for host-embedded biological dynamics

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Abstract

Classical theoretical biology studies trajectories of interacting populations: growth, competition, coexistence, oscillation, invasion, and persistence. In many biomedical applications, however, those interacting populations are embedded within a host whose progression, organ failure, or death is the endpoint of interest. This changes the mathematical problem. We develop a general framework in which an internal biological state evolves according to a mechanistic dynamical system, while host-level risk is determined by a harmful state derived from that internal state. Event times arise through a hazard map, so survival is determined by cumulative hazard over time. Within this framework we prove a curvature principle: if the hazard map is convex, then among trajectories with the same temporal mean of the harmful host state, cumulative hazard is minimized by the non-oscillatory trajectory and strictly increased by genuine oscillations. A convex-order formulation extends this result to mean-preserving spreads, and a small-oscillation expansion shows that survival loss is proportional to local curvature and temporal variance. A simple numerical illustration makes the mechanism transparent. These results expose a general endpoint mismatch: strategies that improve control-style endpoints such as time to a burden threshold can nevertheless worsen survival by sustaining cyclical exposure to risky states. We discuss the framework through a competitive Lotka-Volterra cancer model and a pathogen-immune-damage model. The paper provides a general bridge between dynamical systems theory and time-to-event analysis and identifies hazard curvature as the key determinant of when oscillatory biological dynamics help or harm host outcomes.

Keywords: time-to-event; survival; hazard; dynamical systems; ecology; host-embedded ecology; adaptive therapy; host-pathogen interactions; disease tolerance; Jensen's inequality

1. Introduction

Classical theoretical biology is primarily concerned with the dynamics of interacting populations. In predator-prey, competition, consumer-resource, and related systems, the central objects of study are the internal state variables themselves: whether populations coexist, oscillate, stabilize, invade, or go extinct. By contrast, in many biomedical applications the corresponding “species” are embedded within a larger system, the host, and the clinically meaningful endpoint lies at that higher level. Tumour clones compete within a patient, and cancer is now widely framed as an ecological and evolutionary process [1]. Pathogens and immune effectors likewise interact within a host, but the clinically meaningful outcome depends on host damage, resistance, and tolerance rather than on microbial counts alone [2-4]. In each case the internal ecological game matters because of what it does to the host.

This distinction is mathematically important. A mechanistic dynamical system produces a trajectory. A medical endpoint, however, is usually a time-to-event outcome: progression, hospitalization, organ failure, or death. Statistical methodology for linking longitudinal trajectories to event times has existed for decades. Joint longitudinal-survival models connect repeated measurements to hazard through shared latent structure [5,6]. Mechanistic versions couple nonlinear ordinary differential equation models to event-time processes in applications such as HIV and prostate cancer [7,8]. More recently, survival methodology has represented the hazard itself using ordinary differential equations and related dynamical constructions [9,25]. At a different biological scale, survival dynamical systems have shown how population-level epidemic models can be reinterpreted as individual-level survival and hazard functions [10]. These approaches show that linking trajectories to events is not new. What remains less developed is a general theoretical interpretation of what dynamical properties, especially oscillation, imply for host survival once a hazard map is specified.

A parallel idea exists in ecology. Jensen’s inequality and the broader literature on nonlinear averaging show that variability can change average performance whenever the relevant response function is nonlinear [11-13]. If the response is convex, variability increases its temporal average; if it is concave, variability lowers it. This principle is well known in ecological theory, but it has not been developed as a general time-to-event theory for host-embedded biological dynamics.

We will refer to such settings as host-embedded ecology: the modelled populations form an internal ecological system, but the endpoint of interest is a host-level event process generated by that internal state. In host-free ecology, the modelled populations are themselves the endpoint. In host-embedded ecology, they are internal actors whose trajectories matter because they induce host-level risk.

That omission matters because many biomedical applications of ecological theory are inherently host-embedded. Competitive ecological models have been used to motivate cancer containment and adaptive therapy [14-18]. The foundational adaptive therapy paper by Gatenby and colleagues explicitly framed the problem as maintaining a tolerable tumour burden by exploiting competition between sensitive and resistant populations [15]. More recent work has extended that literature through questions of turnover, patient-specific scheduling, and optimized treatment timing [20-22]. Yet the true objective in these settings is not simply prolonged coexistence or delayed threshold crossing of internal populations; it is improved host outcome. Our earlier work in adaptive therapy highlighted a specific version of this problem by

showing that once survival is linked to cumulative burden, control-style success need not translate into better prognosis [19]. The present paper generalizes that observation.

The main idea is simple. Suppose an internal biological system generates oscillations in a harmful host state, such as tumour burden, inflammatory damage, or toxicity. If host hazard is a convex function of that harmful state, then time spent near peaks matters disproportionately. In that case, oscillatory control can look attractive on state-based endpoints while still worsening cumulative hazard and reducing survival. The key issue is therefore not oscillation *per se*, but oscillation viewed through the curvature of the host hazard map.

The aims of this paper are fourfold. First, we formulate a general framework coupling mechanistic biological dynamics to host event risk. Second, we derive a curvature principle showing that under convex hazard, oscillatory trajectories are intrinsically costly relative to smoother trajectories with the same temporal mean. Third, we show how this principle clarifies two biomedical settings: competition-based cancer treatment and pathogen-immune interactions with host damage. Fourth, we provide a simple numerical illustration that makes the mechanism concrete for readers outside mathematical ecology.

2. Methods

2.1 General host-embedded framework

Let $x(t) \in \mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ denote the internal biological state at time $t \geq 0$. This state may represent tumour subclones, pathogen and immune populations, microbial guilds, or any other interacting populations. Let $u(t) \in \mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ denote an externally imposed control, such as treatment intensity or environmental forcing. We assume the internal state evolves according to

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x(t), u(t), \theta), x(0) = x_0.$$

In many applications the host is affected not by the full internal state directly but by one or more derived harmful variables. We therefore define a host-level harmful state

$$z(t) = h(x(t), u(t), \eta),$$

where $z(t) \in \mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$. Examples include total tumour burden, inflammatory damage, organ dysfunction, or a weighted combination of disease burden and treatment toxicity. In some settings z itself may satisfy additional dynamics,

$$\dot{z}(t) = \Phi(x(t), z(t), u(t), \eta),$$

but for the present theory the key object is the resulting path $z(\cdot)$.

We suppose a host event time is generated through an instantaneous hazard

$$\lambda(t) = g(z(t)),$$

with cumulative hazard

$$\Lambda(t) = \int_0^t \lambda(s) ds = \int_0^t g(z(s)) ds,$$

and survival function

$$S(t) = \exp[-\Lambda(t)].$$

This formulation is intentionally broad. It contains current-value hazard models, cumulative-damage formulations, multivariate risk states, and composite maps that incorporate both disease burden and treatment burden. It also makes explicit that two distinct layers are involved: the internal dynamical system and the host-risk map g .

2.2 Analytical approach

For clarity we first consider the scalar case $m = 1$, writing the harmful host state simply as $z(t)$. The main results are derived by comparing trajectories through the cumulative-hazard functional

$$\Lambda_I[z] := \int_I g(z(t)) dt,$$

defined for any integrable trajectory z on an interval I . The primary analytical tools are Jensen's inequality, convex order, and a second-order Taylor expansion. Throughout, the hazard map is assumed nonnegative and sufficiently smooth where required.

The goal is not to estimate a particular hazard function from data, nor to optimize a specific treatment policy numerically, but to derive structural results that hold across a wide class of host-embedded dynamical systems. The worked examples are therefore used as theoretical illustrations rather than as fitted case studies. The numerical example in Section 3.6 is included only to make the generic mechanism visually and quantitatively explicit.

2.3 Worked example systems

Two model classes are used to interpret the general theory.

2.3.1 Competitive Lotka-Volterra cancer model

A two-clone tumour composed of treatment-sensitive cells x_S and treatment-resistant cells x_R is represented by

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_S &= r_S x_S \left(1 - \frac{x_S + \alpha x_R}{K}\right) - \kappa u(t) x_S, \\ \dot{x}_R &= r_R x_R \left(1 - \frac{x_R + \beta x_S}{K}\right).\end{aligned}$$

The host-relevant burden is defined as

$$z(t) = x_S(t) + x_R(t),$$

with host hazard

$$\lambda(t) = g(z(t)).$$

This generic structure captures competition-based ecological models of cancer in which treatment suppresses sensitive cells, competition suppresses resistant cells, and treatment scheduling is used to preserve competitive restraint [14-22].

2.3.2 Pathogen-immune-damage model

A within-host pathogen model with pathogen burden P , immune response I , and cumulative host damage D is represented by

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{P} &= r_p P - \alpha P I, \\ \dot{I} &= \frac{\beta P}{1 + \gamma P} - \delta I, \\ \dot{D} &= \sigma_p P + \sigma_I I - \rho D.\end{aligned}$$

The host hazard may be written as

$$\lambda(t) = g(D(t)),$$

or more generally as $\lambda(t) = g(P(t), I(t), D(t))$. This generic structure captures the central idea of resistance and tolerance frameworks: host outcome depends not only on pathogen abundance, but on the interaction between pathogen, defence, and damage [2-4,23].

3. Results

For clarity we first consider the scalar case $m = 1$, writing the harmful host state simply as $z(t)$.

3.1 The curvature principle

Define the horizon-specific cumulative hazard functional

$$\Lambda_I[z] := \int_I g(z(t)) dt$$

for any integrable trajectory $z: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where I is an interval.

Theorem 1 (Curvature principle). Let g be convex. For any integrable trajectory z , define its temporal mean

$$\bar{z} = \frac{1}{|I|} \int_I z(t) dt.$$

Then

$$\Lambda_I[z] \geq |I| g(\bar{z}).$$

If g is strictly convex, equality holds if and only if z is constant almost everywhere on I .

Proof. Let Z be the random variable obtained by sampling the trajectory $z(t)$ uniformly over I . Then $\mathbb{E}[Z] = \bar{z}$, and

$$\frac{1}{|I|} \Lambda_I[z] = \mathbb{E}[g(Z)].$$

By Jensen's inequality,

$$\mathbb{E}[g(Z)] \geq g(\mathbb{E}[Z]) = g(\bar{z}).$$

Multiplying by $|I|$ gives the result. If g is strictly convex, equality occurs only if Z is almost surely constant, which is equivalent to z being constant almost everywhere on I . \square

This theorem yields an immediate biological interpretation. If host hazard is convex in the harmful host state, then among all trajectories with the same temporal mean, the least variable trajectory minimizes cumulative hazard and maximizes survival. Oscillation is therefore intrinsically costly under convex hazard.

3.2 Linear, convex, and concave regimes

Theorem 1 separates three qualitatively different regimes.

Corollary 1.

1. If g is linear, then $\Lambda_I[z]$ depends only on the temporal mean \bar{z} .
2. If g is strictly convex, then any nontrivial oscillation around a fixed temporal mean strictly increases cumulative hazard.
3. If g is concave, the inequality reverses, and variability can reduce cumulative hazard.

The key determinant is thus the curvature of the hazard map rather than oscillation alone.

3.3 Convex-order formulation

Theorem 1 compares a trajectory to the constant path with the same mean. A broader comparison is possible using convex order.

Let Z_1 and Z_2 denote the random variables induced by two trajectories z_1 and z_2 under uniform sampling over I . If $Z_1 \leq_{cx} Z_2$, meaning that Z_2 is a mean-preserving spread of Z_1 in convex order [24], then by definition

$$\mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z_1)] \leq \mathbb{E}[\varphi(Z_2)]$$

for every convex test function φ for which the expectations exist.

Proposition 1 (Convex-order hazard ordering). If $Z_1 \leq_{cx} Z_2$, then for every convex hazard map g ,

$$\Lambda_I[z_1] \leq \Lambda_I[z_2].$$

Thus, the correct comparison principle is not merely oscillatory versus non-oscillatory, but less versus more variable in convex order.

3.4 Small-oscillation expansion

The curvature principle also has a local form that is useful for interpretation.

Suppose

$$z(t) = \bar{z} + \varepsilon \xi(t), \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T \xi(t) dt = 0,$$

with ε small and $g \in C^2$ near \bar{z} . A Taylor expansion yields

$$g(z(t)) = g(\bar{z}) + \varepsilon g'(\bar{z})\xi(t) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} g''(\bar{z})\xi(t)^2 + O(\varepsilon^3).$$

Integrating over $[0, T]$ and using the zero-mean condition gives

$$\Lambda_T[z] = Tg(\bar{z}) + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} g''(\bar{z}) \int_0^T \xi(t)^2 dt + O(\varepsilon^3).$$

Remark 1 (Small-oscillation penalty). To second order, the cumulative-hazard effect of oscillation is proportional to the local curvature $g''(\bar{z})$ and the temporal variance term $\int_0^T \xi(t)^2 dt$. If $g''(\bar{z}) > 0$, then small oscillations around \bar{z} are harmful to survival.

This makes the biology transparent: local convexity converts variance into hazard.

3.5 Endpoint mismatch

Many control problems are not optimized for survival directly. Instead, they are assessed using state-based endpoints, for example the first time a burden variable exceeds a threshold B :

$$\tau_B[z] = \inf \{t \geq 0 : z(t) \geq B\}.$$

This is generally not equivalent to optimizing survival.

Proposition 2 (Threshold-survival mismatch). There exist increasing convex hazard maps g , thresholds B , and trajectories z_1, z_2 such that

$$\tau_B[z_1] > \tau_B[z_2]$$

but

$$S_1(T) < S_2(T)$$

for some clinically relevant horizon T .

Proof. Take $B = 1$ and $g(z) = z^2$, and fix $T > 1$. For parameters $\eta > 0$ and $\delta > 0$, define

$$z_2(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq t < 1, \\ 1 + \eta, & 1 \leq t \leq T, \end{cases} z_1(t) = \begin{cases} 0.9, & 0 \leq t < 1 + \delta, \\ 1 + \eta, & 1 + \delta \leq t \leq T. \end{cases}$$

Then $\tau_B[z_2] = 1$ and $\tau_B[z_1] = 1 + \delta$, so z_1 appears better on time-to-threshold. But

$$\Lambda_T[z_1] - \Lambda_T[z_2] = \int_0^1 (g(0.9) - g(0)) dt + \int_1^{1+\delta} (g(0.9) - g(1 + \eta)) dt.$$

The first term is strictly positive. The second term is negative, but it can be made arbitrarily small in magnitude by choosing δ sufficiently small. Hence, for sufficiently small δ ,

$$\Lambda_T[z_1] > \Lambda_T[z_2].$$

Therefore

$$S_1(T) = e^{-\Lambda_T[z_1]} < e^{-\Lambda_T[z_2]} = S_2(T).$$

So, a trajectory can delay threshold crossing while worsening survival through cumulative exposure. \square

This proposition is important for applications. Time to progression, time to maximal burden, time to relapse, or related control-style endpoints can disagree with survival whenever the hazard depends nonlinearly on the full path and not merely on a crossing time.

3.6 A simple numerical illustration

A compact numerical example makes the curvature principal concrete. Consider the horizon $T = 2$, the two trajectories

$$z_{\text{flat}}(t) = 1, z_{\text{osc}}(t) = 1 + 0.6 \sin(2\pi t),$$

and the convex hazard map

$$g(z) = z^2.$$

Both trajectories have the same temporal mean, namely 1. Over the interval $[0, 2]$, the oscillatory trajectory completes two full periods, so direct integration gives

$$\Lambda_2[z_{\text{flat}}] = \int_0^2 1^2 dt = 2,$$

whereas

$$\Lambda_2[z_{\text{osc}}] = \int_0^2 (1 + 0.6 \sin(2\pi t))^2 dt = 2 \left(1 + \frac{0.6^2}{2}\right) = 2.36.$$

Hence

$$S_{\text{flat}}(2) = e^{-2} \sim 0.14, S_{\text{osc}}(2) = e^{-2.36} \sim 0.09.$$

Thus, the oscillatory trajectory has lower survival probability despite having the same mean burden. This example is deliberately simple, but it makes the generic mechanism vivid: under convex hazard, equal mean does not imply equal survival.

3.7 Worked example 1: competitive Lotka-Volterra cancer dynamics

The competitive cancer model provides a natural application of this argument. In such models, continuous treatment suppresses sensitive cells strongly and thereby risks competitive release of the resistant clone, whereas adaptive or containment-style treatment attempts to preserve competition by allowing burden to fluctuate within a tolerated range [14-22]. On a purely ecological reading of the internal dynamics, this can appear attractive because it prolongs coexistence and delays unrestrained resistant expansion.

The present framework shows why this ecological intuition does not automatically translate into a survival benefit. If g is convex in tumour burden, then recurrent oscillations in z carry a direct cumulative-hazard penalty. Therefore, even when adaptive treatment prolongs time to a progression threshold, it may still worsen survival unless the ecological benefit of delaying resistance outweighs the curvature-induced cost of maintaining repeated excursions into higher-risk burden states.

This observation generalizes a more specific point previously made in a cancer adaptive-therapy setting: once survival is linked to cumulative burden, control-style success need not translate into better prognosis [19]. Here the result is model-independent. It does not depend on a particular parameterization or a particular cancer type; it follows from the combination of host-embedded dynamics and convex hazard.

A useful design principle follows immediately. Suppose two treatment protocols, u_A and u_B , generate burden paths z_A and z_B over I with identical temporal means,

$$\frac{1}{|I|} \int_I z_A(t) dt = \frac{1}{|I|} \int_I z_B(t) dt,$$

but z_A is less variable than z_B in convex order. Then for any convex g ,

$$\Lambda_I[z_A] \leq \Lambda_I[z_B].$$

Thus, if two protocols achieve the same average burden but one does so by maintaining cyclical fluctuations while the other yields smoother suppression, the smoother protocol is favoured for host survival under convex hazard.

This does not imply that continuous maximal dosing is always optimal. Rather, it shows that any benefit from preserving competition must be weighed against a mathematically unavoidable curvature penalty if that preservation is achieved through recurrent high-burden excursions. Put differently, a regime can be ecologically successful in the sense of containment [17] and yet still be inferior for host survival if it relies on repeated movement into convex-risk states.

3.8 Worked example 2: pathogen-immune-damage dynamics

The pathogen-immune-damage model shows that the same argument applies outside cancer. In this setting the clinically relevant state is not pathogen abundance alone, but host damage generated jointly by pathogen burden and immune response [2-4]. A control strategy that creates repeated inflammatory or damage spikes may still look acceptable when judged by mean pathogen burden, or even by a threshold defined on pathogen load, yet perform poorly on survival if host hazard is convex in damage.

In this system, interventions or host traits may improve outcome in at least two qualitatively different ways. Resistance acts mainly by reducing pathogen burden. Tolerance acts mainly by

reducing the translation of internal dynamics into host damage or by improving repair. These are conceptually distinct, and recent within-host models increasingly make explicit that pathogen dynamics, damage accumulation, and host survival can be separated in exactly this manner [23].

The curvature principle gives a direct prediction. If g is convex in damage, then recurrent inflammatory flares or damage oscillations are intrinsically costly even if the mean pathogen load is acceptable or a severe-load threshold is crossed only late. In other words, a treatment or host response that repeatedly overshoots into high-damage states can perform poorly on survival even when it appears to maintain pathogen control.

This example also clarifies the role of local convexity around homeostasis. In some infections, risk may not increase monotonically from zero. Instead, there may be an optimal physiological neighbourhood in which host function is preserved, with risk increasing when damage becomes too high. Around such a homeostatic point D^* , the hazard can still be locally approximated as convex,

$$g(D) \approx g(D^*) + g'(D^*)(D - D^*) + \frac{1}{2}g''(D^*)(D - D^*)^2,$$

provided g is twice differentiable and $g''(D^*) > 0$. The small oscillation result then implies that fluctuations around D^* are harmful to second order. Thus, the relevant objective is not simply pathogen elimination, but stabilization of the host near a low-risk physiological regime.

This is particularly important for infections or inflammatory diseases in which immune pathology contributes substantially to outcome. In such systems, low average pathogen burden is not sufficient if achieved through repeated damaging immune overshoots.

4. Discussion

The central claim of this paper is that when ecological or evolutionary dynamics occur inside a host, the mathematically natural endpoint is no longer the internal trajectory alone, but the host event process generated by that trajectory. This simple observation has strong consequences.

First, it creates a bridge between several literatures that have largely developed in parallel. Biostatistics has long known how to link longitudinal biomarkers to time-to-event outcomes [5-9]. Survival dynamical systems have shown that even population-level dynamical models can imply individual-level survival laws [10]. Ecology and mathematical biology have long known that curvature determines the consequences of variability [11-13]. Host-embedded biological dynamics require these ideas at once. The resulting synthesis is that hazard curvature determines whether oscillatory internal dynamics are beneficial, neutral, or harmful for host survival.

Second, the framework explains why familiar control-style endpoints can mislead. Time to a burden threshold, time to progression, or time to relapse depend on selected features of a trajectory. Survival depends on the whole path through cumulative hazard. These objectives need not align. A strategy that improves one may worsen the other.

Third, the theory suggests a useful conceptual distinction between host-free ecology and host-embedded ecology. In host-free ecology, the modelled populations are the endpoint. In host-embedded ecology, the modelled populations are internal actors whose dynamics affect a

larger system that carries the event process. Cancer, infection, microbiome-associated disease, and immune-mediated pathologies all fit naturally into this latter category.

Fourth, the framework helps clarify the place of adaptive therapy in cancer theory. The adaptive-therapy literature has asked when ecological containment is possible, when turnover or resistance costs matter, and how patient-specific treatment timing should be chosen [15-22]. The present theory is complementary. It asks a different question: even if an ecological strategy succeeds in delaying resistant escape or threshold crossing, what does that imply for host survival once cumulative hazard is made explicit? Under convex hazard, the answer is: not necessarily what one hopes.

The paper is intentionally general and has several limitations. First, the main theorem is mathematical rather than empirical. Its biological usefulness therefore depends on estimating or justifying the relevant hazard map in concrete applications. Second, the worked examples and numerical illustration are conceptual rather than fitted. Their role is to show how the general principle operates, not to make disease-specific therapeutic recommendations. Third, the present analysis is deterministic. Real within-host systems may exhibit demographic stochasticity, environmental noise, measurement error, or random variation in host vulnerability. The curvature logic still suggests that convex hazard penalizes high-risk excursions disproportionately, but under stochastic dynamics survival depends on the distribution of full paths, not only on temporal means and variances. Fourth, the scalar harmful-state formulation is only the simplest case. Real systems may require multivariate host-risk states that combine disease burden, inflammation, organ damage, and treatment toxicity. In that setting, the Jensen comparison extends directly when $g: \mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is jointly convex, or in common separable cases where $g(z) = \sum_i g_i(z_i)$ with each g_i convex. Marginal convexity alone is not sufficient. Finally, if the hazard map varies with time, so that $\lambda(t) = g_t(z(t))$, then the curvature principle still holds pointwise whenever each g_t is convex in z , but comparisons become sensitive to *when* excursions occur, not only how large they are.

This paper is also not claiming to be the first attempt to link longitudinal dynamics with time-to-event outcomes. That space already includes classical joint models, mechanistic joint models, survival dynamical systems, and recent dynamical formulations of the hazard, including oscillatory hazard families [5-10,25]. Nor is the inequality in Theorem 1 itself novel; it is a direct application of Jensen's inequality and sits naturally within standard stochastic-order theory [11-13,24]. The contribution here is the general host-embedded interpretation: once a mechanistic internal model is paired with a host hazard map, the curvature of that map becomes a first-order determinant of whether oscillatory trajectories are desirable.

5. Conclusion

When ecological or evolutionary dynamics are transplanted into medicine, the interacting populations are typically not the endpoint of interest. They are embedded within a host whose progression or survival is what matters. Once that nesting is recognized, time-to-event analysis becomes part of theoretical biology rather than merely a statistical add-on. The translation from internal dynamics to host outcome is governed by a hazard map, and the curvature of that map determines the cost or benefit of variability. Under convex hazard, oscillations are intrinsically costly. Hazard curvature is therefore the key quantity that links mechanistic biological dynamics to host survival.

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